

Formation Constants of Iron(III) Complexes with Serinehydroxamic Acid and Threoninehydroxamic Acid in Mixed Aqueous Organic Solvents

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The present study is in continuation of our earlier work¹ on proton-ligand stability constants of serinehydroxamic acid and threoninehydroxamic acid in aqueous organic mixtures. A survey of literature² indicates that no work has been done on Fe^{III} complexes with serinehydroxamic acid (SerHA) and threoninehydroxamic acid (ThrHA). The present work has been carried out on the determination of formation constants of the Fe^{III} complexes with threoninehydroxamic acid (ThrHA) and serinehydroxamic acid (SerHA) in aqueous as well as methanol-water, isopropanol-water, ethanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures at constant mole fraction (0.24) of organic solvent in aqueous-organic media at ionic strength of 0.2 M (NaCl).

Results and Discussion

Representative titration curves of pH versus volume of NaOH added for several titrations are shown only for SerHA in dioxane-water medium (Fig. 1). The stability constants (Table 1) for the complexes were evaluated from the plots of \bar{n} versus pL . Complexation between Fe^{III} with SerHA and ThrHA initiates at about pH 2.9 the values of \bar{n} lies between 0 and 2. The ratio of stepwise formation constants, i.e. $\log K_1/K_2$ was found to be > 2.5 suggesting thereby that the formation of ML and ML₂ complex species are independent steps. The order for stability con-

Fig. 1. Titration curves for serinehydroxamic acid (SerHA) and Fe^{III}-SerHA in dioxane-water at 0.24 mole fraction of organic solvent at 0.2 M NaCl ionic strength : (X) acid only, (O) acid + SerHA and (•) acid + SerHA + Fe^{III}.

tants $\log K_1 > \log K_2$ indicates a decrease in bond strength with successive attachment of the ligand. A comparison of present $\log K_1$ values with $\log K_1$ 9.2 for Fe^{III}-serine³ and $\log K_1$

8.6 for Fe^{III} -threonine³ systems shows that SerHA and ThrHA formed complexes of greater stability than the corresponding amino acids, serine and threonine in aqueous medium. The greater stability of amino acid hydroxamates complexes may be attributed to the strong binding of CONHO^- with Fe^{III} due to greater basic nature as compared to COO^- binding with Fe^{III} in amino acids.

Both the Fe^{III} -SerHA and Fe^{III} -ThrHA systems were studied in different mixed aqueous organic solvents at same mole fraction (0.24) of the organic solvent and at constant ionic strength of 0.2 M (NaCl). The trend in variation of log

Fig. 2. Variation in $\log \beta_2$ values vs $1/D$ for (O) Fe^{III} -SerHA and (●) Fe^{III} -ThrHA systems in aqueous organic mixtures: AQ (aqueous), M-W (methanol-water), E-W (ethanol-water), I-W (isopropanol-water), D-W (dioxane-water).

β_2 versus $1/D$ was studied (Fig. 2). The values generally increase with increase in $1/D$. This indicates that dielectric constant (D) plays the major role in the magnitude of the stabilities, and the interactions between metal and ligand are predominantly ionic. The $\log \beta_2$ values for Fe^{III} -SerHA and Fe^{III} -ThrHA systems decreased in various solvents in the order: dioxane-water > isopropanol-water > ethanol-water > methanol-water > water. This sequence is parallel to the order of dielectric constant of the media: dioxane-water < isopropanol-water < ethanol-water < methanol-water < water. In both the systems, the increase in the $\log \beta_2$ values with increase in $1/D$ (Table 1) in mixed solvents is similar to that in case of proton-ligand stability constants of SerHA and ThrHA ($\log K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\log K_2^{\text{H}}$) reported by us¹ in various aqueous organic mixtures at constant mole fraction (0.24) of organic solvent at constant ionic strength 0.2 M NaCl at 25°. The results also show that SerHA formed complexes of greater stability than ThrHA with Fe^{III} in aqueous as well as in aqueous organic solvents and this could be due to steric hinderance caused by side-chain substituents in ThrHA, as the $\log K_2$ values are less to an appreciable extent in ThrHA compared to SerHA in each medium.

Experimental

DL-Serinehydroxamate (2-amino-*N*,3-dihydroxypropanamide) and DL-threoninehydroxamate (2-

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Fe^{III} COMPLEXES WITH SerHA AND ThrHA IN MIXED AQUEOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS

Solvent composition (% v/v)	Mole of organic solvent	$1/D$	SerHA				ThrHA			
			$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_1/K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_1/K_2$
Aqueous	0	0.013 0	11.72	9.01	20.73	2.71	11.79	7.24	19.03	4.55
Methanol-water 42.5 : 57.5 (v/v)	0.24	0.016 7	11.85	9.11	20.96	2.74	11.91	7.45	19.36	4.46
Ethanol-water 51.8 : 49.2 (v/v)	0.24	0.019 8	12.00	9.25	21.25	2.73	12.15	7.60	19.75	4.55
Isopropanol-water 58.6 : 41.4 (v/v)	0.24	0.029 0	13.13	9.97	23.10	3.16	12.76	7.75	20.51	5.01
Dioxane-water 61.2 : 38.8 (v/v)	0.24	0.039 9	13.70	10.10	23.80	3.60	13.00	9.00	22.00	4.00

* Standard deviations of $\log \beta$ values are ± 0.03 .

amino-*N*,3-dihydroxybutanamide) (Sigma) were used. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. pH-metric titration technique of Irving and Rossotti⁴ was used to determine formation constants. Solutions (20 ml) containing (a) $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ HCl, (b) (a) + $1.7 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand; (c) (b) + $3.4 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe^{III} solution, were separately titrated against 0.1 *N* NaOH in water, methanol-water (42.5 : 57.5, v/v), ethanol-water (51.8 : 49.2, v/v), isopropanol-water (58.6 : 41.4, v/v) and dioxane-water (61.2 : 38.8, v/v) mixtures keeping ionic strength at 0.2 *M* (NaCl) as well as at constant mole fraction (0.24) of organic solvent in aqueous organic media.

An ECIL 5652 pH meter with combined glass and calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements and pH values in aqueous-

organic media were corrected⁵. The values of dielectric constant (*D*) for the solvent composition were either obtained or calculated from the reported data^{6,7}.

References

1. B. S. SEKHON and R. KAUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in press.
2. B. KURZAK, H. KAZLOWSKI and E. FARKAS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **114**, 169.
3. A. E. MARTELL and R. M. SMITH, "Critical Stability Constants", Plenum Press, New York, 1974.
4. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; 1953, 3397.
5. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
6. I. FRANK, J. A. CRITCHFIELD, I. R. GIBSON and J. H. HALL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1991.
7. G. AKERLOFF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 4130.

